

Fatigue life prediction of welded steel components based on geometric scan data

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ABSTRACT

The life cycle assessment of welded steel components subjected to high cyclic loads is usually carried out based on the usual concepts (nominal, structural, and notch stress concept), which only provide rough geometric minimum specifications in the form of weld angles or excess weld metal. These specifications are usually assigned to the corresponding notch cases and empirically derived. This type of estimation allows for a safe design, but on the other hand, it also gives away potential and can lead to a significant underestimation of the actual service life. In addition, these concepts are practically based on decades-old tests that do not reflect the advances in welding technology. In order to better exploit the actual potential of safe and economical steel constructions, it is essential to consider geometry as the most significant influencing factor when dealing with welded joints.

The introduction of efficient scanning systems and powerful finite element methods has increased the interest in considering geometry more closely in recent years. In fact, numerous research projects attempt to use the real geometry of welded joints as the basis for life cycle assessment. While the application of scanning and subsequent FEA calculations are used successfully, new difficulties arise in the form of notch sensitivity. Notch sensitivity is the paradox where the fatigue life decreases disproportionately to the higher stresses due to notch effects.

This paper discusses the state of the art by considering real geometry, the problem of notch sensitivity in the context of scan and mesh resolution, and the corresponding approaches.

Keywords: weld scan, fatigue life, real notch stresses, notch sensitivity

1 INTRODUCTION

The limited service life of metallic components under cyclical loads has been widely accepted for around 200 years and is of great economic relevance. Expensive over-dimensioning is just as unacceptable as under-dimensioning, with an increased risk of failure, costly repairs, and downtimes of structures and supporting structures in civil engineering and mechanical engineering. The service life represents a multi-parameter problem with influences that are difficult to separate and have significant uncertainties. The influences range from geometric notch effects to the choice of material, load size, load sequence, multiaxiality, roughness, surface treatments, temperature, mean and residual stresses, sample size, rolling direction, and corrosion.

Suppose we restrict ourselves to low-strength steels under uniaxial loads at ordinary atmospheric temperatures in welded constructions. In this case, the geometric notch effect, in particular, is of increased relevance, while other influencing factors are only of minor importance.

This was recognized at an early stage of investigations on this subject and resulted in many fatigue classes in the nominal stress concept, generally determined empirically from Wöhler tests. These classes represent a catalogue of geometric details from which the engineer obtains input values as a

permissible stress range for a given number of load cycles (or an allowable number of load cycles for a given stress range).

Early on, it was also recognized that calculating analytical stresses and changing geometries required better concepts. The improvement was ultimately the consideration of the hot spot stress and notch stress concepts, each attempting to evaluate the stresses more locally to improve the safe design. Today, these concepts form the usual triad of stress-based verification methods for welded components in the high-cycle region (HCF), see Fig. 1. However, the fact that all three concepts idealize the most significant influencing factor, namely the direct geometric notch in the seam transition area, remains problematic.

Fig. 1. Nominal stress, hot spot stress and notch stress concepts

Due to the highly costly test procedures, the available underlying fatigue classes (1) are often decades old and have been reprocessed using improved statistical methods (2, 3) but do not quantitatively reflect the geometric differences in the macro area of the seam geometry, which take place, for example, due to the welding position (4) and the improvement in welding technology.

Advances in scanning technology, surface reconstruction and numerical methods of structural mechanics have opened up new possibilities for assessing service life in recent years. Volume models can be obtained from scan data on which corresponding stresses or stress ranges can be calculated directly and thus form the basis for service life evaluations.

Recently, such concepts have gained popularity and are increasingly used (5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12). However, this opens up new problems, which are discussed in the following chapters.

Chapter 2 describes the transfer of the geometry into scan data, the reconstruction of the surfaces, and the structural-mechanical calculation. Chapter 3 discusses the problem of notch sensitivity and the possibility of translating these described problems into a consistent concept. Chapter 4 shows the workflow, and Chapter 5 illustrates a simple classification example.

2 GEOMETRY, SCANNING AND STRESS CALCULATION

The first step in assessing the service life based on the actual geometry is to take a scan. The scanners used vary; as a rule, laser scanners exist in the form of table models, arm-guided models, or a combination of the two. What they usually have in common is a high resolution and accuracy, depending on the model, down to the micrometer range, sometimes down to the range in which continuum mechanical calculations lose their validity. The accuracy of the scanning systems is usually statistically analyzed and refers to a corresponding significance level.

In our research, a system from the company FARO (13) with a resolution of 0.05mm and an accuracy of 0.035mm (with a statistical significance of twice the standard deviation) is used for this purpose.

The point clouds obtained this way are usually triangulated and cleaned from scanning errors. The subsequent steps vary depending on the type of further analysis. This ranges from polygonal

sectioning for 2D observation to direct conversion of the surface meshes into FE elements for 3D analyses. Here, problems already become apparent in advance in the course of further structural-mechanical calculations. When using the raw scan data directly, the powerful mesher of the FE solver with its focus on elements with good metrics (mesh metrics) is only available to a limited extent, and the number of elements is enormous due to the high scan resolutions. However, the most serious disadvantage is the unavoidable mathematical singularity that occurs with further structural-mechanical calculations due to concave shapes with angles $<180^\circ$. A very high resolution does not fundamentally avoid this problem; it is just less visible.

In our research, we use a different approach by converting the point cloud into many NURBS patches connected in a C1-continuous (i.e. tangent-continuous) manner. This approach means that the subsequent FE meshing is independent of the raw scan data. A suitable choice of elements can avoid the mathematical singularities at reentrant concave corners.

The calculation of the mechanical stresses is based on this step. By using NURBS, local mesh refinements can also be carried out manually or using adaptive mesh convergence checks. Elements with quadratic (or higher) displacement and boundary shape functions are suitable as FE elements. For our calculations using Ansys (14), the isoparametric 10-node tetrahedron element SOLID187 with a quadratic shape function is ideally suited and is also used.

Fig. 2 shows the process from the geometry to the scan data to the FE calculation.

Fig. 2. From geometry to FEA

3 NOTCH SENSITIVITY

The stresses obtained in Chapter 2 cannot be interpreted directly as fatigue-effective stresses or stress ranges. When evaluating fatigue in notches, notch sensitivity must also be considered. Notch sensitivity is the paradox that the decrease in service life does not occur to the same extent as the increase in stresses due to the notch effect. This effect goes back to the work of Thum (15), Siebel/Stieler (16, 17) and Neuber (18, 19). While Siebel considers the stress gradient, Neuber considers the integral over a length in the notch root. He introduces the concept of a microstructural support length, which he regards as an intrinsic parameter of the material.

Numerous other approaches, also of a phenomenological nature, have emerged over many decades. Some examples of these approaches are shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Notch sensitivity approaches: a) Siebel/Stieler (16, 17), b) Neuber (18), c) Peterson (20), d) Sheppard (21), e) Neuber (18), f) Kuguel (22)

All approaches are deterministic in their methodology, except for the approach in Fig. 3f: This approach is a probabilistic method that evaluates the maximum loaded volume and can also be seen as a way of additionally considering the statistical size effect. The maximum notch stresses are converted into a reduced effective fatigue stress σ_{eff} (Eq. (1)) using a factor η_k .

$$\sigma_{eff} = \eta_k \cdot \sigma_k \quad (1)$$

The deterministic methods have in common that they evaluate a stress value of some kind at a certain distance from the notch ("Theory of Critical Distances"). Taylor (23, 24) describes this in detail. The magnitude of the distance is crucial and can be obtained using two methods: It is derived from a physical quantity, and the material's grain size lends itself to this. This approach seems particularly tempting, as it is known that the fatigue strength correlates with the grain size (25). Unfortunately, this results in two problems: The grain size varies within a specific range in the weld area (26), and there is the need which value of grain size should be used. A smaller grain size leads to a higher tensile strength via the Hall-Petch relationship, which leads to a higher fatigue strength or a larger acceptable number of cycles. However, considering a smaller distance in the concepts of notch sensitivity leads to an increase in fatigue-effective stress and, thus, a reduction of acceptable cycles. This physical transfer is, therefore, inversely proportional, and obviously wrong. The other method, which seeks the geometric variable that leads to the lowest scatter in the statistical evaluations, is a fitting without a physical background. This procedure leads to a purely phenomenological approach without actual physical connection (27). The calculation of this parameter proves to be a relatively trivial problem within a research paper or project. Still, the back-calculated parameters are surprisingly different in magnitude across numerous research papers. This problem is familiar and can be traced back to the first back-calculations by Siebel (16) and Neuber (18, 19) who came to very different results for their support lengths.

Yao (28) and Zhang (29) generalized the approaches to account for notch sensitivity and described them as special cases of a yet unknown higher theory and concluded that the fatigue effective stress is a function of the surrounding local stress field (see Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Near field around the notch

However, these existing methods are difficult to apply to scanned irregular surfaces. While Kaffenberger (5) still applies Neuber's approach (Fig. 3b) to scanned surfaces and stumbles across numerous new problems (including self-penetrations and ambiguous integration paths at convex outer edges), more recent work is moving in the direction of fundamentally numerically realizable approaches. One particularly suitable method - the IGM ("implicit gradient model") - will be discussed here. The IGM is based on the work of Peerlings (30, 31). The IGM calculates the effective stress σ_{eff} according to Eq. (2) using a weighting function G in the vicinity of the notch and the local stress σ_k as well as a scaling function Ψ :

$$\sigma_{eff}(\vec{x}) = \frac{1}{\Psi(\vec{x})} \int_V G(\vec{x}, \vec{x}) \sigma_k(\vec{x}) dV_{\vec{x}} \quad (2)$$

If a suitable weighting function G (Gaussian function) is used, equation (2) can be simplified considerably and leads to Eq. (3).

$$\sigma_{eff}(\vec{x}) - a \nabla^2 \sigma_{eff}(\vec{x}) = \sigma_k(\vec{x}) \quad (3)$$

The exact derivation is extensive and can be found in Peerlings (32). The advantage of Eq. (3) is that it converts from an integral to a differential equation. The latter has the advantage that it can be solved using standard FEA software packages, which are, in fact, differential equation solvers. This calculation can be done on the same mesh and following the mechanical stress calculation. In analogy to Zhang (29), the result is the calculation of an effective notch stress σ_{eff} , including the local stress field, as shown in the other conventional approaches in Fig. 3.

The parameter a in Eq. (3) is a measure of the weighting function in the vicinity of the notch, see Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Parameter a and its influence on the weight function (33)

If only the IGM is used, the statistical size effect usually needs to be included separately. This effect can be subsequently added to scanned structures, for example, using a probabilistic approach (e.g. Weibull model), see Eq. (4); another method is shown in Fig. 3f. The approach evaluates the

probability of failure at surface A with the partial surfaces A_i . In this case, the result is the probability of failure P_f as a function of the load cycles N_{cycle} .

$$P_f = 1 - \prod P_s(\Delta\sigma_i, A_i, N_{cycle}) \quad (4)$$

Eq. (4) generally contains a Wöhler line with corresponding characteristics. The partial areas A_i usually assign areas to corresponding nodes on the FE mesh. This assignment is not unambiguous; popular methods are methods of roof determination or via the element shape functions.

Fig. 6. Areas of influence A_i to the node N_i with $\sigma_{eff,i}$ of FEA (1)

4 WORKFLOW AND DEPENDENCIES

Based on the principles outlined in chapters 2 and 3, fundamental dependencies and interactions for the entire process emerge. Fig. 7 shows the possible process steps.

Fig. 7. Possible process steps

The dependence of the results is fundamentally linked to the scan resolution. While the inaccuracies lead to too large or too small radii, a scanning resolution that is too low leads to smaller notch radii and, thus, to lower stresses (see Fig. 8) and higher calculated lifetime.

Fig. 8. Real edges and reconstructed edges on a notch: a) coarse resolution, b) inaccurate measurement

5 CLASSIFICATION EXAMPLE

This chapter illustrates a simple example (Fig. 2). This is a flange intersection made of a steel S235 JR (FAT40 according to EN1993-1-9 (34)), and the welding process is 136 (according to (35)). The nominal stress is $\Delta\sigma = 50 \text{ N/mm}^2$. The lifetime in the single-stage fatigue test was 1.301.009 cycles at $R = 0,5$.

Fig. 9. Specimen IF7-1: a) photo, b) NURBS, c) mesh, d) notch stresses and e) effective notch stresses ($a = 0.02\text{mm}^2$)

The FE calculation (see Fig. 9) leads to Fig. 10, which clearly shows the smoothing character of Eq. (3) and the nominal stress.

Fig. 10. Notch stresses and effective notch stresses accumulated on the surface for different parameters a

The parameters used for classification are taken from (36) and are calculated using several heterogeneous test series. The classification uses a linear Wöhler line with $\Delta\sigma_{CR}$ as the reference value at $2 \cdot 10^6$ cycles and a slope m (see Table 1). The probabilistic calculation is omitted in this example.

Table 1. Parameters and calculated lifetime N_{calc}

a [mm ²]	σ_{eff} [N/mm ²]	$\Delta\sigma_{CR}$ [N/mm ²]	m [-]	N_{calc} [-]
0,0000	489	341	2,46	824.960
0,0001	382	333	2,67	1.386.267
0,0005	340	314	2,72	1.610.853
0,0010	321	301	2,73	1.677.868
0,0050	274	261	2,67	1.756.572
0,0100	250	241	2,63	1.816.154
0,0200	226	220	2,58	1.865.867
0,0300	211	208	2,54	1.928.561
0,0500	193	193	2,50	2.000.000
0,0700	181	183	2,47	2.055.030

The best prediction is obtained in the range of small values of a , which is not atypical: the equivalent structure lengths tend to be lower in recent publications (9, 37).

6 CONCLUSIONS

The assessment of the fatigue strength of welded joints based on actual geometric data represents a novel possibility for classification. However, it is associated with new problems and is still complex to apply. Still, it is a logical further development with significant potential to evaluate the actual weld geometry beyond any idealization - and subsequently to be able to assess the quality of welds directly.

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